

Supplemental data for

Weise, S., Blattner, F. R., Börner, A., Dehmer, K. J., Grübe, M., Harpke, D., Lohwasser, U., Oppermann, M., Stein, N., Willner, E., Nagel, M. (2025). The German Federal Ex Situ Genebank for Agricultural and Horticultural Crops – Conservation, exploitation and steps towards a bio-digital resource centre. *Genetic Resources (S2)*, 91–105. doi: [10.46265/genresj.GYDY5145](https://doi.org/10.46265/genresj.GYDY5145).

Supplemental Table 1: Collecting trips by German-speaking researchers. This includes collecting trips involving the institute itself as well as those from which material was obtained by way of seed exchange or which was incorporated into the collections at a later date. The table is based on information of (Hammer et al. 1994) and (Hammer 2020) and has been expanded by information from the genebank archives to include additional collections. Only collecting trips from which at least 30 accessions are currently preserved in the German genebank are listed. This list does not claim to be exhaustive and is constantly being updated.

Year(s)	Collecting area	Collector(s)
1922-1932	Alpine region	E. Mayr; Alpine landrace collection; integrated into the genebank from 1964
1928-1932	Anatolia	K.O. Müller, M. Klinkowski, O. Schwarz, A. Scheibe and others; Expeditions of the Biological Research Centre Berlin-Dahlem in the context of the establishment of agricultural research facilities in Turkey
1935-1936	Hindu Kush	A. Scheibe, K. v. Rosenstiel, W. Roemer and others; German Hindu Kush Expedition; integrated into the genebank from 1946
1937-1938	Northwest India/Nepal	A. Herrlich and others
1938-1939	Tibet	E. Schäfer, K. v. Rauch; German Tibet Expedition
1941-1942	Albania, Greece (incl. Crete), Yugoslavia, Hungary	H. Stubbe and others; Balkan collecting trips; integrated into the genebank from 1943
1950	Southern Italy	R. Maly, G. Pascher
1952-1954	Iran	H. Kuckuck; six FAO collecting trips; integrated into the genebank from 1956
1956/1958/1959	China	H. Stubbe, R. Mansfeld, H. Böhme, S. Danert, P. Hanelt and others; three journeys, first major collecting trips of the Gatersleben institute
1958	El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras	F. Schwanitz; Central America collection; integrated into the genebank from 1960
1959/1960	Ethiopia	H. Kuckuck; integrated into the genebank from 1960
1962/1964	Mongolia	H. Böhme, S. Danert and others
1974/1977/1981	Slovakia and Moravia	P. Hanelt, K. Hammer, J. Schultze-Motel and others; landrace collections
1975/1980	East Germany	K. Hammer, P. Hanelt, C. Tittel and others; landrace collections
1976/1978	Poland	P. Hanelt, J. Schultze-Motel; landrace collections
1977	Georgia	K. Hammer, P. Hanelt
1978	Southwest Spain	C. Lehmann, K. Hammer and others

1980-1992	Northern Italy, Southern Italy, Sicily	K. Hammer, C. Lehmann, P. Hanelt and others; various collecting trips
1981-1990	Georgia	P. Hanelt, J. Kruse, R. Fritsch and others; various landrace collections
1981/1982/1983	Libya	K. Hammer, C. Lehmann and others; three collecting trips
1982/1983/1986	Austria	C. Lehmann, F. Scholz, R. Schachl, W. Kainz and others; landrace collections
1982/1983	Ethiopia	R. Steuckardt
1983	Ethiopia	H. Mebus
1983/1984/1987	Tadzhikistan	P. Hanelt, R. Fritsch and others; various collecting trips
1984	Ethiopia	C. Lehmann
1984	Poland	K. Hammer; landrace collection
1985/1987	Mongolia	P. Hanelt, J. Kruse, K. Pistrick and others
1985-1997	Central Asia (Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan)	P. Hanelt, R. Fritsch, K. Pistrick, M. Fischer, F. Speta; various collecting trips
1985-1989	North Korea	K. Hammer; various collecting trips
1985/1986	Iraq	K. Hammer; various collecting trips
1986-1993	Cuba	K. Hammer, T. Gladis; various collecting trips
1986/1988	China	P. Hanelt; together with Botanical Institute of the Academia Sinica
1988	Colombia, Peru	K. Hammer, G.K. Müller
1991	Altaj	K. Pistrick
1992/1993	Tunisia	K. Pistrick
1992/1993/1994	Romania	K. Hammer, H. Rosso, K. Pistrick, N. Friesen; various trips
1993/1995	Sardinia	K. Hammer, T. Gladis
1993/1994/1995	Albania	K. Pistrick, K. Hammer, T. Gladis; various trips
1993	Poland	E. Willner
1994	Iran	R. Fritsch
1994-2000	Italy	K. Hammer; various trips
1994-1998	Spain (Canary Islands, Mallorca, southern Spain)	J. Keller, K. Pistrick, K. Hammer, R. Fritsch, G. Kern and others; various trips
1995	Turkey	R. Fritsch, N. Friesen
1995	Germany (Altmark)	E. Willner
1995	South Uzbekistan	K. Pistrick
1996/1997	Croatia	E. Willner; two journeys
1997	South Tibet	S. Beck
1998	Bulgaria	E. Willner, B. Schmidt, K. Wiege
1999	Northern Spain	E. Willner, B. Schmidt
1999	Azerbaijan and Iran	L. Frese and others
2001	France	E. Willner, B. Schmidt
2002-2010	Georgia	K. Pistrick, R. Fritsch, B. Gemeinholzer and others; various collecting trips
2002	Ireland	E. Willner, B. Schmidt
2006	Bavarian Forest / Bohemian Forest	E. Willner
2012	Jordan	I. Thormann, U. Lohwasser and others
2017	Swiss Alps	E. Willner, B. Boller
2023-2024	Germany	S. Fritsch, T. Engst, A. Krumbiegel and others

Supplemental Table 2: Recent third-party-funded projects under participation of the IPK genebank.

Acronym	Funding agency	Time period	Aim	Crops
EURISCO	ECPGR	2014–2028	Hosting and maintenance of the European Search Catalogue for Plant Genetic Resources	All maintained in European PGR collections
GrassLandscape	EC	2015–2018	Bridging landscape genomics and quantitative genetics for a regional adaptation of European grasslands	Perennial ryegrass
DRYeGRASS	BLE	2016–2018	Genetic analyses of drought stress tolerance	Perennial ryegrass
GrasFest	BLE	2017–2020	Phenotypic screening of seed retention and histological analyses	Perennial ryegrass and meadow fescue
EUCLEG	EC	2017–2021	Breeding forage and grain legumes to increase EU's and China's protein self-sufficiency	Legumes
Farmer's Pride	EC	2017–2021	Networking to enhance <i>in situ</i> conservation of European PGR	No specific
GenRes Bridge	EC	2019–2021	Joining Forces for genetic resources and biodiversity management	No specific
InnoLuteus	FNR	2019–2022	Improving cultivation of yellow lupin	Yellow lupin
LinSel	BLE	2019–2022	Selection of lentil genotypes suited for sustainable cropping systems	Lentil
P Starch	FNR	2019–2022	Assessment of nitrogen uptake efficiency in starch potatoes	Potato
P Legumes	WGL	2019–2023	Analysis of P efficiency in forage legumes and their capacity to utilize P from recycling products	Alfalfa, red clover
EffiKar	BLE	2020–2024	Assessment of nutrient uptake efficiency in table varieties	Potato
AGENT	EC	2020–2025	Development of an activated genebank network	Mainly wheat and barley
INCREASE	EC	2020–2026	Development of new approaches for conserving, managing and characterising PGR	Legumes
EVA	ECPGR	2021–2022	Development of technical infrastructure of the European Evaluation Network	Carrot, legumes, lettuce, maize, pepper, wheat and barley
SPITFIRE	Cornet	2021–2024	Screening of pea accessions for PNYDV resistance	Pea
LuzNutz	BLE	2021–2024	Exploring genetic diversity and improving cultivation of alfalfa	<i>Medicago</i> sp.
PotEND	DFG	2022–2025	Evaluation of endophytes in potato cryosamples	Potato
PreLuteus	FNR	2022–2025	Development of high-yielding and resistant pre-breeding lines of yellow lupin	Yellow lupin

CiLaKlima	BLE	2022–2025	Screening of genetic resources of chickpea and grass pea	Chickpea, grass pea
PRO-GRACE	EC	2023–2025	Development of a concept for a European Research Infrastructure for PGR	No specific
Garli-CCS	ECPGR	2023–2025	Development of a garlic conservation and cryopreservation strategy	Garlic
WiLGer	BLE	2023–2026	Winter lentil genetic resources to breed winter lentils	Lentil
SiMultAnG	BLE	2023–2026	Ensuring multifunctionality in forage production through species richness in intensive grasslands	Various crops
Legume Generation	EC	2023–2027	Boosting innovation in breeding for the next generation of legume crops for Europe	Legumes
Wick4 Pig	BLE	2023–2028	Seed vetch grains for fattening pigs as an alternative high-protein feedstuff under changing climatic conditions	Vetch
COUSIN	EC	2024–2028	Development of a roadmap for using CWR for breeding and farming	Cereals, legumes, leafy greens, vegetables, oilseed crops
ObiVonKnobi	BLE	2024–2028	Pheno-/chemotypic evaluation and utilisation of garlic	Garlic
DiPisum	BMBF	2024–2028	Digitalisation-driven development of Saxony-Anhalt into an innovation hub for pea breeding, cultivation and processing	Pea
KarOLa	BLE	2024–2029	Assessment of nutrient uptake efficiency and drought stress tolerance	Potato
POMORROW	BMBF	2025–2029	Improving genetic traits using potato genetic resources and new breeding techniques	Potato

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